

FUNCTIONS OF ENCLITIC PRONOUNS IN SA'DI'S GULISTAN

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Abstract. In Gulistan, Sa'di employs enclitic pronouns (ضمایر متصله) with notable grammatical and stylistic flexibility. These pronouns not only indicate possession or relational belonging but also serve syntactic and pragmatic functions that contribute to the text's poetic and rhetorical style.

Key words: Enclitic Pronouns, possessive suffixes, compound verbs.

In Persian grammar, there are pronouns that are attached to the base of a word and are referred to as enclitic pronouns. Functionally and grammatically, they somewhat correspond to possessive suffixes in the Uzbek language. However, the functions of enclitic pronouns in Persian are broader than those of possessive suffixes in Uzbek. While possessive suffixes in Uzbek are added only to nominal elements, Persian enclitic pronouns can attach not only to nouns but also to verbal predicates, prefixes, conjunctions, adverbs, and even words that indicate negation.

Moreover, in addition to expressing possession or belonging from a morphological and grammatical perspective, enclitic pronouns serve several other functions, which we will elaborate on below. It is worth noting that this section focuses specifically on how enclitic pronouns function when attached to compound verbs.

Enclitic pronouns often attach to either the noun part or the verb part of compound verbs formed by a noun + verb model. Accordingly, they can be classified into two groups:

- a) Enclitic pronouns attached to the noun part.
- b) Enclitic pronouns attached to the verb part.

All three person forms of both singular and plural enclitic pronouns can attach to the noun part of compound verbs. In the following verse, the enclitic pronoun -at (ات) is observed once attached to the noun part of a compound verb and once to the word hič (none):

ای که هرگز فرامشت نکنم
هیچت از بنده یاد می آید؟

Ey ke hargez farāmešat nakonam

Hičat az bande yād miāyad? (G. p. 146).

Meaning: *O you whom I never forget, do you ever remember me?*

The use of enclitic pronouns with other types of pronouns and certain conjunctions is a distinct feature specific to classical texts.

In the following sentence, the third-person singular enclitic pronoun -aš (اش) is attached to the noun part of a compound verb:

آهنگ خدمتش کردم دربان رها نکرد و جفا کرد و معذورش داشتم که لطیفان گفته اند.

Āhang-e xedmataš kardam darbān rahā nakard wa jafā kard wa ma'zuraš dāštam ke latifān gofteand. (G. p. 100)

Translation: *I desired to serve him, but the doorkeeper did not allow me in and was harsh. I forgave him, for the wise have said so.*

In the next sentence, the first-person singular pronoun -am (ام) is attached to the noun part of a compound verb:

گر گرفتارم کنی مستوجب
ور بیخشی عفو بهتر کانتقام.

Gar gereftāram koni mastawjibam

War bebaxši afw behtar k-enteqām. (G. p. 401)

Meaning: *If you find me guilty, I deserve it; but if you forgive, forgiveness is better than revenge.*

It is well known that language strives for brevity and efficiency. Enclitic pronouns appear in context as shortened forms of personal pronouns. As seen in the examples, when enclitic pronouns are added to the noun part of a compound verb, they act as shortened versions of personal pronouns in the accusative or dative case, clarifying their meaning within the sentence.

Although our primary focus is on enclitic pronouns attached to the noun part of compound verbs, we also consider those attached to the verb part.

In modern spoken Persian, it is quite common for enclitic pronouns to attach to verbal predicates. For example: دیدمتون (*didametun*) – "I saw you (plural/formal)." This pattern emerges from the constant tendency in speech for brevity and conciseness.

In Sa'di's *Gulistan*, some instances occur where the verb part of a compound verb carries an enclitic pronoun:

بلطف اندک اندک بیدار کردش که خیز آفتاب بر آمد.

Belotf andak andak biydār kardaš ke xiz āftāb bar āmad. (G. p. 401)

Translation: *He gently woke him up, saying, "Rise, the sun has come up."*

In some cases, infinitive forms of compound verbs also contain enclitic pronouns:

بوسه دادن بروی دوست چسود؟

هم درین لحظه کردنش بدرود

Buse dādan beruy-e dust če sud?

Ham dar in lahze kardanaš bedurud. (G. p. 379)

Meaning: *What good is kissing the face of a friend, if at that very moment you bid farewell?*

In the above sentence, the compound verb *bedurud kardan* (to bid farewell) takes the enclitic pronoun *-aš* (اش). In Persian, regardless of the structural form of the verb, when it appears in its infinitive form, it behaves like a noun – just like in Uzbek – and can take on noun-specific morphological markers.

The attachment of enclitic pronouns to the verb part of a sentence often results from metrical demands in poetic texts.

Apart from the aforementioned examples, *Gulistan* contains compound verbs with unique conjugation patterns. Some Iranian linguists refer to these as impersonal intransitive verbs, treating them as a distinct group based on their structure. However, these are essentially compound verbs that differ morphologically from others.

This distinction is reflected in their conjugation: in impersonal intransitive verbs, the verb part is always in the third-person singular, while the subject is indicated by the enclitic pronoun attached to the noun part.

Such examples are also found in *Gulistan*, where verbs like *āmadan* (to come), *gereftan* (to take), and *bordan* (to carry) are used to form intransitive compound verbs:

چنانکه حکایت کنند که عربی را درمی چند گرد آمده بود و بشب از تشویش لوریان در خانه خوابش نمی برد.

Čonānke hekāyat konand ke arabirā derami čand gerd āmade bud wa bešab az tašwiš-e luriyān dar xāne tanhā xābaš namibord. (G. p. 302)

Translation: *It is told that an Arab had collected some dirhams, but due to the worry of thieves, he could not sleep alone at night in his house.*

In the following examples, a compound verb formed with *āmadan* includes the pronouns *-aš* (اش) in one case and *-at* (ات) in another:

ملک بار دیگر بر و دل خوش کرد و عمل فرمود قبولش نیامد.

Malek bār-e digar bar u delxuš kard wa amal farmud qabulaš nayāmad. (G. p. 87)

Translation: *The king once again showed kindness and appointed him to a post, but he did not accept it.*

گفتم: آن نوبت اشارت من قبولت نیامد که گفتم: عمل پادشاهان چون سفر دریاست خطر ناک و سودمند یا گنج بر گیری یا در طلسم بمیری.

Goftam: Ān noubat ešārat-e man qabūlat nayāmad ke goftam: Amal-e pādšāhān čun daryāst xatarnāk wa sudmand yā ganč bar giri yā dar talassom bemiri. (G. p. 99)

Translation: *I said, “That time you did not accept my advice when I said: The actions of kings are like the sea—dangerous yet profitable: you may either seize a treasure or perish in the whirlpool.”*

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the multifunctional role of enclitic pronouns in Persian, particularly within compound verb constructions. Unlike Uzbek possessive suffixes, which are restricted to nominal attachment and express only possession, Persian enclitic pronouns are syntactically versatile. They can attach to nouns, verbs, adverbs, conjunctions, and even negative particles, reflecting Persian’s capacity for morphological economy. In compound verbs, enclitic pronouns may be affixed to either the noun or verb component, depending on grammatical or stylistic factors.

This is especially evident in classical Persian texts such as Sa’di’s *Gulistan*, where poetic meter often influences pronoun placement. Overall, enclitic pronouns serve as concise markers of person, possession, and syntactic function, offering a unique insight into Persian’s structural efficiency and expressive capacity.

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